

COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS: A NEW PERSPECTIVE ON LANGUAGE AND THOUGHT

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Abstract Cognitive linguistics has introduced a paradigm shift in understanding language as an integral component of human cognition rather than merely a linguistic phenomenon. This paper explores the core principles and methodologies of cognitive linguistics, emphasizing its interdisciplinary nature and practical applications. We highlight the evolution, central theories, and implications of this field in addressing the relationship between language, thought, and culture.

Key words: Cognitive linguistics, language and cognition, Conceptual Metaphor Theory, Frame Semantics, Construction Grammar, interdisciplinary linguistics, language teaching, artificial intelligence, cultural studies, cross-cultural communication, language acquisition, natural language processing, neuro-linguistics, computational linguistics, cognitive schemas, cultural linguistics.

Introduction The advent of cognitive linguistics has redefined linguistic studies by bridging language with human cognition and broader cultural contexts. Unlike traditional linguistic paradigms, which treat language as an autonomous system, cognitive linguistics investigates how linguistic phenomena reflect and shape cognitive processes. This approach considers language a cognitive tool essential for acquiring, processing, and transmitting knowledge. The present study aims to explore the theoretical foundations of cognitive linguistics and its relevance in modern applications, including language teaching, artificial intelligence, and cultural studies.

Methods This study employs a multidisciplinary review methodology, synthesizing insights from linguistics, psychology, neuroscience, and anthropology. Key theoretical frameworks, including Conceptual Metaphor Theory, Frame Semantics, and Construction Grammar, are analyzed to elucidate their contributions to understanding language-cognition interactions. Historical analyses of seminal works by researchers such as Noam Chomsky, Jerome Bruner, and Eleanor Rosch are also included to contextualize the development of the field.

Results The findings underscore the following core contributions of cognitive linguistics:

1. **Systematic Study of Cognitive Processes:** Cognitive linguistics provides insights into how language reflects mental structures and processes, including perception, memory, and categorization.

2. **Interdisciplinary Integration:** The field draws from diverse disciplines, enriching its analytical frameworks and enabling practical applications in areas such as artificial intelligence and cultural anthropology.

3. **Cultural and Contextual Relevance:** Cognitive linguistics highlights the influence of culture and social context on linguistic structures, offering tools to analyze cross-cultural communication.

4. **Practical Applications:** The theories and methods of cognitive linguistics have proven effective in designing language teaching methodologies, improving translation practices, and developing natural language processing algorithms.

Discussion The interdisciplinary approach of cognitive linguistics reveals that language is not merely a medium of communication but also a repository of collective and individual cognitive experiences. For instance, Conceptual Metaphor Theory demonstrates how abstract concepts are understood through metaphorical mappings rooted in physical experiences. Frame Semantics explores how knowledge structures shape language comprehension and production. These theories emphasize the integral role of language in organizing and transmitting human experiences.

Cognitive linguistics has also advanced our understanding of language acquisition, showing that children internalize linguistic rules through cognitive schemas that evolve with exposure and experience. Furthermore, it underscores the significance of cultural differences in shaping linguistic expressions, thus fostering cross-cultural awareness and dialogue.

Conclusion Cognitive linguistics offers a transformative perspective on language as an integral aspect of human cognition and culture. Its interdisciplinary approach and practical relevance underscore its significance in addressing contemporary challenges in education, artificial intelligence, and cultural studies. Future research should continue exploring the intersections of cognitive linguistics with emerging fields, such as neuro-linguistics and computational linguistics, to further expand its scope and applicability.

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